

SITE GS/SPHINX	DATE 7/4/79	AREA NE	SQUARE N2/W1	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top: ≈ 10.64	Bottom: 10.57
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter: 15cm N-S 13cm E-W		Width:	Length:	Depth: 8cm

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
①	ALLUVIAL MUD	DARK GREY	PACKED	FINE	T	Lm	Gp
					O	Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
D	Al						
	Other						
	T	Lm ✓ FLECKS	Gp				
	O	Gr	Char 2 tiny FLECKS				
Do							
Ba							
D	Al						
	Other						
	T	Lm ✓ Frags Thru out	Gp				
	O	Gr ✓ 2 small Frag 0.5 x 1 cm largest	Char				
Do							
Ba							
D	Al						
	Other						
	T	Lm	Gp				
	O	Gr	Char				
Do							
Ba							
D	Al						
	Other						
	T	Lm	Gp				
	O	Gr	Char				
Do							
Ba							
D	Al						
	Other						
	T	Lm	Gp				
	O	Gr	Char				
Do							
Ba							
D	Al						
	Other						

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ 2 No./ 24, 25	B&W: Roll/ 2 No./ 16, 17
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DRAWN	Area Plan: 1:20 PLAN	Feature Plan:	Sections: 1:2 w/ Fill
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: ④ Really as pockets-veins thru out ③
 ③ Seems whiter, softer Gypsum (slightly) than that as found in other cuttings - where yellowish to buff w/ charcoal flecks. May be charcoal in ③ but few and fine.

This gypsum not well packed into hole - rather a "glob"
 Bedrock slightly reddened bottom of hole.